

CHOICE PROJECT

Descriptive data for schools

No	District	
1	School name	
2	School location (urban, rural, semi-urban)	
3	Ownership (public, government aided)	
4	Number of students at school (secondary)	
5	Number of teachers at school (secondary)	
6	School performance	

Descriptive data for Teachers

Date: _____

School _____

district _____

No	How old are you? (Age)	
1	Gender? (Male/Female)	
2	What is your level of Education? (Masters, bachelor's degree (A0), Advanced diploma (A1), advanced level Certificate (A2), or other.....)	
3	How long have you worked as a secondary school teacher? (No. of years in teaching profession)	
4	What main subjects do you teach at school?	
5	How many periods (lessons) do you teach per week?	
6	What is your average class size (how many students are in your class on an average day?)	